

STAGES OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE INSTITUTE FOR REGULATORY IMPACT ASSESSMENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article analyzes the formation and evolution of the regulatory impact assessment (RIA) system in Uzbekistan, structured across four key stages from 2006 to the present. Emphasis is placed on institutional reforms, legal frameworks, and the adoption of international standards. The role of the Ministry of Justice, the implementation of digital tools, and the introduction of mandatory RIA procedures are highlighted. The study concludes that RIA has become a vital mechanism for enhancing regulatory quality, legal predictability, and public policy efficiency.

Keywords: Regulatory Impact Assessment (RIA), legal reform, smart regulation, regulatory governance; ex-ante and ex-post assessment, normative legal acts, institutional development, public policy analysis, administrative law.

The Republic of Uzbekistan is taking a number of important measures aimed at systematizing and improving the process of evaluating regulatory legal acts. Over the past period, the objectives of the ODS have been determined. The main objective of this procedure is to identify the possible consequences of the adoption of a regulatory act or restrictions for entrepreneurs and other interested parties. This was an important step in preventing unnecessary pressure on businesses and increasing regulatory transparency.

In 2006-2007, the republic began to form the foundations for the introduction of the institute for regulatory impact assessment. This period is characterized by an initial initiative to study international experience and introduce best practices aimed at improving the business climate in the country. The key event of this stage was the signing of a memorandum of cooperation with the International Finance Corporation. This memorandum played an important role in integrating the international experience and principles of ODS into the regulatory and legal activities of Uzbekistan. The establishment of the ODS implementation working group and the conclusion of the memorandum became the basis for further steps to form the legal and organizational infrastructure necessary for the successful implementation of regulatory impact assessment.

In 2008-2014, the active phase of the establishment of the ODS institute in Uzbekistan began. This period was marked by the adoption of a number of key documents and initiatives aimed at improving the business climate and increasing the transparency of law-making activities. The adoption of documents simplifying licensing and issuing permits, and the consolidation of the principle that regulations that complicate business conditions come into force no earlier than three months after publication, have become important steps towards improving the business environment. These measures allowed entrepreneurs to prepare for the changes and minimize the negative consequences of the sudden entry into force of the new regulations.

One of the significant innovations was the requirement to post all acts related to business interaction on the official websites of government agencies. This requirement has significantly increased the transparency and accessibility of information for entrepreneurs. The introduction of the Unified Portal of Interactive Public Services (EPIG) allowed entrepreneurs to make suggestions and comments on draft regulations, which ensured the participation of businesses in the process of their development. Also during this period, the procedure for assessing the impact of developed and existing regulations on business activities was introduced, which provided a systematic analysis and improvement of regulations.

Since 2018, the period of active development of the ODS institute has begun, during which systematic measures have been taken to streamline and improve law-making activities. The approval of the concept of improving normative activity has become a key event of this stage. The concept focused on creating a systematic legislative framework, eliminating legal conflicts and ensuring the stability of legal regulation. The main directions were to improve the quality of the preparation of regulatory legal acts, the introduction of modern technologies into the legislative process and the introduction of the principles of "smart regulation".

An important step in this period was the mandatory implementation of ODS for regulations affecting business activities. Attention was also focused on the implementation of international experience in conducting mandatory regulatory impact assessments, which made it possible to analyze the impact of laws on competition and predict their consequences. The introduction of a unified electronic system for the development and approval of draft regulations has greatly simplified the process of their review and increased transparency.

Since 2021, Uzbekistan has entered a new period of further development of the institute for regulatory impact assessment. This stage is characterized by the adoption of a number of measures aimed at systematizing and improving the process of evaluating regulatory legal acts. The adoption of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-5025 dated March 15, 2021 was an important step in this direction. The Resolution established a specific procedure for conducting an ODS and defined the goals and exceptions associated with conducting an assessment. In accordance with the document, the mandatory conduct of ODS was established for regulations affecting business activities, with the obligation to justify the refusal to conduct an assessment in exceptional cases .

One of the significant innovations was the definition of the Ministry of Justice as the coordinator of all RIA activities. The Ministry of Justice has become responsible for methodological support and coordination of the work of government agencies and other organizations responsible for conducting the assessment. The ODS methodology was also approved, which regulated two approaches: "ex-ante" for drafts of new regulations and "ex-post" for existing acts. These methods include analyzing alternatives, calculating benefits and costs, and conducting public discussions.

The adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Regulatory Legal Acts" in a new edition dated April 20, 2021, consolidated the assessment of regulatory impact as a set of measures aimed at identifying and assessing the consequences of the adoption of regulatory acts. The legislative consolidation of the regulatory impact assessment has provided a more structured approach to the analysis of the effectiveness and efficiency of regulations.

When comparing different approaches to the periodization of the development of ODS in Uzbekistan, the opinion of domestic scientists was studied and a comparative analysis of various approaches was carried out. For example, some Russian scientists adhere to the following approach to the periodization of ODS and identify three key stages: preparatory (2008-2018), formation (2018-2019) and further development (from 2020). As you can see, in this case, attention is focused on the gradual strengthening of the institutional framework and the complication of regulatory impact assessment mechanisms. While our approach includes four stages, starting in 2006, with an emphasis on specific legislative acts and reforms.

The difference between the approach presented in this paper is a more detailed description of specific measures and legislative changes at each stage,

such as the introduction of an electronic project approval system and the principles of "smart regulation".

In this regard, it should be noted that the development of the institute for regulatory impact assessment in the Republic of Uzbekistan is a multifaceted process, including preparatory, formative, developmental and modern stages. Each of these stages is characterized by special achievements and challenges that have contributed to the improvement of law-making activities and the creation of a more transparent and predictable business environment.

The measures taken, such as the approval of specific RIA procedures, the creation of an assessment methodology and the development of an electronic system, have become important steps towards improving the quality of regulation and improving the effectiveness of standard-setting activities. At the same time, a comparative analysis of various approaches to the periodization of the development of ODS highlights the importance of an integrated and multifaceted approach to the assessment and improvement of legal systems.

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